

With Reagent-I, ions like Pt(II), Pd(II), Ni(II), V(V) and oxalate interfere.

With Reagent-II, Pd(II), Cu(II), Fe(III), V(V), Ni(II), SCN⁻, Citrate, Tartrate, HF₂⁻ however interfered the complex system.

However, to overcome interference due to cations, there are recommended procedures¹⁰ by a prior distillation of Os(VIII) in HNO₃ medium as OsO₄.

Degree of dissociation, dissociation constant and stability constant

Using the equation of Harvey and Manning¹¹, the degree of dissociation and dissociation constant were calculated and found to be 0.184 and 1.79×10^{-6} for Reagent-I and 0.159 and 1.27×10^{-6} for Reagent II respectively.

Stability constants were calculated^{12,13} from molar ratio data according to Leden's method¹⁴. Using the following equation: $\phi = 1 + \beta_1[L] + \beta_2[L]^2 + \dots + \beta_n[L]^n$, where $\phi = \frac{CM}{[M]}$ for the equation $M + nL = ML_n$. The value of the function, ψ_1 is obtained from the equation¹⁴,

$\psi_1 = \frac{\phi - 1}{[L]} = \beta_1 + \beta_2[L] + \dots$ for 1 : 1 (M : L) systems $\psi_1 = \beta_1$.

Stability constants were also evaluated by Rosenstein's method¹⁵.

For 1 : 1 metal-ligand system at an wave length where metal and reagent have no or negligible absorbance, i.e.,

$$\epsilon_0 = \epsilon_L \approx 0,$$

$M + L \rightleftharpoons ML$, stability constant β_1 is given by

$$\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_1 - \epsilon} = \beta_1[L]$$

In both the cases notations have their usual significance. β_1 was evaluated graphically in both the cases and found as follows :

	Reagent-I	Reagent-II
Stability constant calculated by,—		
(i) Leden's method	1.3×10^6	0.90×10^6
(ii) Rosenstein's method	2.5×10^6	2.0×10^6
Mean β_1	1.9×10^6	1.45×10^6

Results and Discussion

The benzothiazole reagent could satisfactorily be used for spectrophotometric determination of osmium with limited interference and is suitable for routine laboratory analysis. The Schiff's base anil reagent though cannot tolerate a number of foreign

ions in the system, it is the first one of a series of di-anils. Other reagents which have already been utilised by the authors, where $-\text{CH}_3$ groups of the diketones have been replaced by other radicals to give more sensitive and selective reagents for determination of osmium. These reagent are not only restricted for use to osmium only but could be extended to the field of other platinum metals, such as Pt and Pd. Such studies are in progress in this laboratory. The authors have already prepared three more reagents by condensing benzoylacetone, dibenzoyl methane and thenoyl trifluoro acetone with 2-aminothiophenol and their studies on osmium and other platinum metals will be reported shortly.

References

1. A. K. MAJUMDAR and J. G. SENGUPTA, *Anal. Chim.*, 1960, **22**, 306.
2. A. K. MAJUMDAR and S. K. BHOWAL, *Anal. Chim.*, 1972, **62**, 223.
3. G. H. AYRES and W. N. WELLS, *Anal. Chim.*, 1950, **22**, 370.
4. W. R. CROWELL and H. D. KIRSCHMAN, *J. Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1928, **9**, 113.
5. A. RINGBOM, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1938, **115**, 332.
6. E. B. SANDELL, *Colorometric Determination of Traces of Metal*, Interscience, New York, 3rd Edn. 1959, p. 84.
7. G. H. AYRES, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, **21**, 652.
8. P. JOB, C. R. ACAD, *Sci.*, 1925, **180**, 928; *Ann. Chim. Paris*, 1928, **9**, 113.
9. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem.; Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
10. F. E. BEAMISH, *Analytical Chemistry of Noble Metals*, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1st. Edn. 1966, p. 399.
11. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488; 1952, **74**, 4744.
12. I. L. LEDEN, *Z. Phys. Chem., A*, 1941, **188**, 160.
13. S. FRONACUS, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1950, **4**, 72.
14. SASWATI P. BAG and ANIL K. CHAKRABARTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 335.
15. L. ROSENSTEIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **31**, 117.

A New Method for the Geochemical Exploration of Trace Amount of Barium and Strontium Using SPADNS

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IN view of the need for a rapid method of the determination of trace amount of Ba and Sr, a direct colorimetric method has been developed using SPADNS¹⁻⁴ for the micro-determination of barium as little as 0.2 μ g and of strontium as little

as 0.3 μ g in 25 ml of final volume with the adjustment of pH using ammonium chloride-ammonia buffer and dil. HCl or dil. NH_4OH .

The method is advantageous because of easy preparation of the reagent, marked colour change from scarlet-red to blue-violet, immediate colour reaction, stability of the reagent and low temperature coefficient.

Experimental

The Ba-SPADNS complex and the Sr-SPADNS complex show maximum absorbance at 570 nm and 560 nm respectively using distilled water as a reference. The absorption maxima of the reagent against water for barium and strontium are 522 nm and 520 nm respectively.

The effect of pH on the absorbance was studied. The maximum absorbance was noticed at pH 10-11 for Ba and pH 8.5-9.5 for Sr respectively. Ammonium chloride-ammonia buffer, dil. HCl or dil. NH_4OH were used for varying pH. The Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.2-60 μ g of Ba and 0.3-60 μ g of Sr respectively. The molar absorptivities of Ba-SPADNS and Sr-SPADNS are 1.3×10^4 (at 570 nm) and 4.3×10^3 (at 560 nm) respectively. No change in optical density was noted for 72 hours for Ba-SPADNS and 4 hours for Sr-SPADNS complexes which suggests that they are sufficiently stable for quantitative determinations.

The sensitivities of the colour reactions are 0.2 μ g Ba per cm^2 and 0.3 μ g Sr per cm^2 (practical) respectively. The stoichiometric composition of the coloured complexes have been determined colorimetrically by adopting the "Slope Ratio Method" and "Job's method"^{5,6} which suggest a 1:1 complex for both the elements with the reagent. Nearly all the elements associated with Ba and Sr were tested to determine the behaviour with SPADNS under the optimum conditions used for Ba-SPADNS and Sr-SPADNS reactions. It has been found that 10 mg amounts of Zn, Fe, Cu, Pb, Ni, V, Nb, Sb, As, Cr, Ga, Ir, Sn, Au, Ag and W do not interfere in the determination of these elements. However, Ca, Mg and Ba in presence of Sr and Sr in presence of Ba interfere seriously.

As the absorption maxima of Ba and Sr are very close to each other, these elements can't be determined by simultaneous spectrophotometry.

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References

1. G. BANERJEE, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1957, 16, 56.
2. G. BANERJEE, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1957, 16, 62.

3. G. BANERJEE, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1974, 271, 284.
4. G. BANERJEE, S. K. KANJI and S. MANDAL, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1976, 28, 247.
5. A. F. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.
6. F. H. POLLARD and J. V. MARTIN, *Analyst*, 1956, 81, 348.

Kinetic Study of Oxidation of Aliphatic Dicarboxylic Acids by Cerium(IV) Ion in Acidic Medium

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A review of the literature shows that the oxidation of aliphatic dicarboxylic acids by cerium(IV) ion has not received much attention. Only recently a preliminary work¹⁻⁴ on the oxidation of oxalic acid, malonic acid has been carried out but the mode of attack of the acids by oxidation species from the Ce(IV) ion has not been worked out, nor the different stages involved, and the effect of $-\text{CH}_3$ group on the overall reaction rate in the process elucidated. Hence, we have undertaken a systematic kinetic study of the oxidation of aliphatic dicarboxylic acids—oxalic, malonic, succinic and glutaric acid by ceric sulphate in acidic medium. Comparative kinetic data of these studies is present in this paper which has enabled us to arrive at a suitable reaction mechanism and the effect of $-\text{CH}_3$ group for this class of reactions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either 'Analar or E. Mercks' guaranteed reagent quality. The stock solution of ceric sulphate was prepared by dissolving a known amount of it in calculated volume of sulphuric acid and diluting with double distilled water. The solutions of the reactive substances were brought to the required temperature in a thermostat, which maintained the temperature at a constant value with in $\pm 0.1^\circ$ and then rapidly mixed. Aliquots were withdrawn at known intervals of time and reaction was stopped by adding ice-cold double distilled water. The estimation of unreacted ceric(IV) was done with standard solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using ferroin as an indicator.

Results

All these reactions have been found to show pseudo first order w.r.t. ceric sulphate. However, the pseudo first order rate constant generally